

STUDY OF THE PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF OLIGOMERIC FLAME RETARDANT TEX-1

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Abstract. *The structure of oligomeric flame retardants of the TEX-1 brand was studied by IR spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction analysis of the location of metal groups in their composition.*

Metal oxides were added to the composition of TEX-1 brand oligomer flame retardant composites containing phosphorus, and the location of metals in the substance was studied by X-ray spatial analysis. According to the results of the analysis of the TEX-1 oligomeric flame retardant, the diffraction reflectance of metals can be analyzed as follows. The research methods were based on X-ray analysis, analysis of the phase composition, as well as the quantitative determination of minerals.

Keywords: *phosphorus, oligomer, flame retardant, composite, metal, X-ray phase, result, analysis, beam.*

Introduction. Currently, the attention to fire-resistant textile materials is increasing in the world, and ensuring fire safety through its wide use as finishing and coatings in the production of household goods, clothing, furniture production, construction, machinery and other industries remains one of the urgent issues. However, along with their many benefits, textile materials that are not treated with flame retardants increase the risk of fire. As a result, there are 7-8 million fires worldwide each year, resulting in 85-90 thousand deaths. In our republic, we can observe that 11,083 fires occurred during 2020, and the number of people who died as a result of fires was 124. These are mainly due to the fact that flammable materials are not protected from fire, which leads to the rapid spread of flame, and the ineffectiveness of fire-protective flame retardants, as well as the development of innovative technologies for their processing into textile materials, which have not yet found a scientific solution. Therefore, great attention is being paid to the development of phosphorus-group oligomeric flame retardants, the creation of their optimal compositions and the improvement of their mechanism of action.

In recent years, improving the flame retardant properties of natural textile materials has become increasingly relevant from year to year. This is because these textile materials are characterized as flammable materials due to their rapid ignition, flame spread, and the release of various smoke and gases. Nevertheless, textile materials are widely used in everyday life, in buildings and structures, in transport and as special protective equipment [1].

Fire-resistant treatment is applied to almost all types of textile products, which allows the use of materials that are perfectly suited to the interior of buildings [2]. Furniture and other interior elements are treated with fabrics and non-woven fabrics for copying, protecting cars, railways, ships, and automobiles from internal equipment [3].

Recently, due to the increasing use of new polymer materials and fabrics in building decoration, the toxicity and density of smoke produced during combustion have increased [4]. To reduce this risk, a number of countries are preparing or have adopted regulations and laws

prohibiting the use of flammable fabrics, primarily overalls, decorative and covering materials, as well as wallpaper and curtain fabrics [5].

Types of fire-resistant fibers created on the basis of modern methods: Fenilon, Arselon, Nomex, Rusar, Arlana, Kevlar, Arimid, etc. Their disadvantages: low hygroscopic indicators, hardness of the material made of them. Therefore, they are rarely used in the textile industry [6].

The most common types of fire and temperature-resistant fibers are: Phenilon, Arimid, Kevlar, Oxalon, SBM, Twaron, Kermel, etc. Comparative characteristics of temperature-resistant fibers are given in Table 1 [7].

Table 1

Comparative characteristics of heat-resistant fibers

Naming of fibers	Oxygen index, %.	Relative breaking strength, gs/tex	Operating temperature, °C
Arimid	40-45	40-60	350
Nomex	28-30	45-50	250
Terlon	28-30	200-210	250
Togilen	28-30	180-210	300
Armos	37-43	90-170	300

These textile materials are available only in the form of yarns and have high flame retardant properties. The manufacturer Ten Cate Protect (Netherlands) produces fire-resistant fabrics based on Nomex aramid fibers on the market [8].

The range of fire-resistant fabrics has three levels of protection, which is achieved using special fibers and impregnations. The latest fabrics protect against flame, high temperatures, molten metals. These textiles are recommended for workers in the oil and gas, metallurgical industries, as well as for overalls for welders, firefighters, and the Ministry of Emergency Situations [8].

Method. Today, it is important to protect people from various negative factors, and special textile materials with high protective properties have a special place here. Special clothing is widely used for fire fighters, oil and gas industry, welders, metallurgists and various manufacturing workers [9].

The IR spectrum of these oligomeric flame retardants shows that the absorption line of organic substances in the region of 2850 cm^{-1} contains absorption lines belonging to the $-\text{CH}_2-$ group, which corresponds to the valence vibrations, and the absorption lines in the region of 1340 cm^{-1} belong to groups containing carbon and hydrogen. Vibrations of all active groups appear in the form of strong narrow lines in the range of 1465 - 1380 cm^{-1} $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}-$.

The IR spectrum confirms the presence of C=S groups at 1460-1300 cm^{-1} and C-C groups at 450-550 cm^{-1} . At the same time, phosphorus bonds in organic compounds can be observed in the regions 1300-1200 cm^{-1} and 1180-1040 cm^{-1} , which are formed by the P=O and P-O-C groups.

The absorption lines in the 1650 cm^{-1} region of the IR spectra indicate the presence of free $-\text{CONH}_2$ groups, and the absorption lines in the 3300-3440 cm^{-1} region indicate the presence of secondary $-\text{CONH}-$ groups.

The assimilation bands between 800 and 1600 cm^{-1} confirm the presence of $-\text{NH}_2$ groups. In addition, intensities appear in the IR spectrum between 600-800 cm^{-1} and 1460 cm^{-1} , which include the binding of metal-containing compounds.

Figure 1. IR spectrum of TEX-1 branded oligomer

According to the results of the analysis of the oligomeric flame retardant TEX-1, the diffraction reflectance of metals can be analyzed as follows. The research methods are based on X-ray analysis, analysis of the phase composition, as well as a method based on the quantitative determination of minerals.

Determination of the phases of the studied materials in high-quality X-ray spatial analysis was carried out in accordance with the literature. The analysis was carried out on a DRON-3.0 diffractometer using a Ni-filter in the range of angles $6 \dots 70^\circ$ under CuK α radiation. X-ray diffraction analysis was obtained at a voltage of 30 kW, a current of 20 mA and an exit slit width of 1 mm. Analysis of the TEX-1 sample with a relative intensity of 14.69556 has the following inter-step distances (d , Å); 11.23191; 8.26088; 6.47164; 4.59894; 3.51383; 3.21142; 3.16613; 2.96136; 2.77989; 2.62767; 2.47606; 2.02714; 1.67791; 1.62572; 1.53719; 1.46702; 1.38972; 1.31766.

Figure 2. X-ray diffraction pattern of TEX-1 oligomer

Figure 2 shows the diffraction pattern of the metal oxide (1.879 Å) and (1.53, 2.80 Å) in the oligomer. The diffraction patterns are given in parentheses. The majority of these metal oxides have a crystalline structure. In this analysis, the metal oxides that form an amorphous structure, which are bonded to organic compounds, urea adducts, and other substances in the composite, show low results in the diffraction of this analysis, indicating that the metal oxides in the oligomeric flame retardant obtained are in a composite state.

Conclusion. The structure of the synthesized oligomeric flame retardants was studied by IR spectroscopy and X-ray analysis of the location of metal groups in the composition, and the fire resistance of textile materials treated with oligomeric flame retardants was determined. The substances added to the flame retardant composition are mainly composite mixtures with synergistic properties.

Metal oxides were added to the composition of TEX-1 brand oligomer flame retardant composites containing phosphorus, and the location of metals in the substance was studied by X-ray spatial analysis.

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